

Mobile Radiation and the Rising Heart Attack Cases in Youth – An Opinion

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Abstract (Summary):

In recent years, there has been a sharp rise in heart attack cases among young people. While many medical and lifestyle factors contribute to this, I believe that one specific and overlooked reason is mobile phone radiation. Continuous use of mobile phones close to the chest may expose the heart to harmful radiation. This radiation, over time, may weaken heart muscles and affect its natural rhythm. If people start using mobile phones by keeping them a little away from the chest, the number of heart attack cases may decrease. Mobile phones are useful devices, but they must be used in a safe and responsible manner.

Main Text:

It is well known that heart attacks occur due to several reasons such as stress, unhealthy food, lack of exercise, and poor sleep. However, I strongly believe that in the case of young people, there is one more hidden cause — mobile radiation. Nowadays, most people use their phones for long hours and often keep them very close to their chest — in shirt pockets or while talking. This brings the source of radiation very near to the heart. Such long-term exposure may gradually weaken the heart muscles, disturb its natural rhythm, and make it more sensitive to stress and fatigue. The solution is simple: use mobile phones wisely. Keep them slightly away from the chest while using or carrying them, use speaker mode or earphones, and avoid sleeping with the phone near the body. Awareness about this small habit can help prevent many heart-related problems in the long run. Mobile is a great invention — but correct use is very important for a healthy life.

Keywords: Heart attack, youth health, mobile radiation, smartphone use, opinion, prevention